

ATTITUDES OF NIGERIANS TOWARDS MUSHROOMS

Abulude, F. Olawale and Yusuf Abdurashed

Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the attitudes of Nigerians towards the consumption of mushrooms. This study was undertaken at the Southwest area of the country. Two hundred respondents were administered with questionnaires. The technique of analysing was by Likert's scale. In the analysis of data, all responses of strongly agree and agree were grouped under agreement, while strongly disagree and disagree were grouped under disagreement. From the results, the respondents showed positive attitudes towards mushrooms. On this note, we recommended that government and private individuals should embark upon the establishment of mushrooms industries. If these are established and sustained, benefits would include employment generation and others.

INTRODUCTION

Edible mushroom (Fig 1) have for a long time been recognized not only as a delicacy, but also for their use as food in man's diets. Mushrooms have been found to be rich sources of protein, lipids, amino acids, glycogen, vitamins and mineral elements [1]. Mushrooms have many uses which range from medicinal, ceremonial, nutritional and biotechnological based functions [2,3]. During the oil boom in Nigeria, these edible mushrooms were abandoned for costly alternatives like meat, fish, snail, fish, etc. As the economic situation of the people is dwindling, many had to source for protein alternatives. The question now is what are the attitudes of Nigerians towards mushrooms intake? In the light of this, we have been prompted to address this issue by embanking on this survey. The aim of this paper is therefore to determine the attitudes shown to intake of mushrooms by Nigerians. Suggestions were made on the outcome.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methods used for the collection of information were adopted from Yeo [3] with slight modifications. Two hundred respondents were contacted within the Southwest of Nigeria. Stratified sampling was used to capture the various subgroups based on age, sex, and income.

Questionnaires

This was divided into section A (demographic information about the respondents – age, sex, religion, occupation, income, marital status etc). Section B (A Likert's instrument). Ten statements were posed to them and they were expected to provide answers either as strongly agree or agree or undecided or strongly disagree or disagree.

Statistical Analysis

The data gathered were analysed using SPSS Statistics 19 by WebSOFT.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One hundred percent response rate was recorded. This could be the interest now shown on the food. Table 1 shows the results. It was observed that statements 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 had 71, 76, 84, 91 and 87.5% agreements rates. These percentages are positive signals towards mushrooms. The values of 62.5 and 82% recorded for disagreement depicted that not all mushrooms are poisonous and majority believed that religion has nothing to do with mushrooms intake. Less than 20% of the respondents were not sure of what to decide. The 42.5% recorded on cultivation and marketing was expected, the reason been that majority of the respondents were civil servants meaning that there may not be enough time for them to cultivate.

In Nigeria, the mushrooms quantities produced or obtained by local farmers are less than intakes of the consumers. It is on this note we are suggesting that stakeholders, government, and researchers should intensify the efforts in cultivating mushrooms on a large scale. Civil servants should be encourage on how to culture so that at their leisure they too can engage on the on the production rather than going to the forest to pick.

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Table 1: Results of attitudes of consumers

No	Statements	Agree	%	undecided	%	Disagree	%
1.	I like the taste when cooked	142	71	15	7.5	43	21.5
2.	I like the text when cooked	152	76	20	10	28	14
3.	Attractive when cooked	168	84	22	11	10	5
4.	I like eating it with different Soups	182	91	10	5	8	4
5.	It is against my religion	15	7.5	21	10.5	164	82
6.	Mushrooms are medicinal	175	87.5	15	7.5	10	5
7.	It is poisonous	25	12.5	20	10	125	62.6
8.	I can cultivate and market	100	50	15	7.5	85	42.5
9.	I prefer it more than meat and fish	110	55	40	20	50	25
10.	Price of mushroom is higher That of meat and fish	10	5	20	10	170	85

Agaricus arvensis

Chloropyllum sp.

Macrolepiota sp.

Pycnoporus cinnabarinus

Tremella fuciformis

Pleurotus porrigens

Pleurotus squarrosulus

icholoma sp

Daldiniacon centrica

Russula sp.

Schizophyllum commune

Scutellinia sp

Thelephora sp

Geastrum saccatus

Microstoma sp.

Unknown

Auricularia auricula.

Fig 1 : Some mushroom resources found in Nigeria (Source: Osemwegie [4])